

Boron Chelate of Salicylhydroxamic Acid

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THE chelating properties of salicylhydroxamic acid and related compounds have been studied by a number of authors. Non metallic chelates of those ligands are rare. This communication deals with the synthesis and study of boron chelate of salicylhydroxamic acid. To an acetone solution of salicyl hydroxamic acid dry trimethyl borate gas was passed at salt-ice temperature. A white precipitate was obtained immediately which was filtered and thoroughly washed with alcohol and then with acetone. (Found : B, 3.08; N, 7.98%. Calculated for $B(C_7H_5O_3N)_2(OCH)_3$: B, 3.1; N, 8.09%.) The compound is sparingly soluble in methanol and ethanol and decomposes completely in aqueous solution. An infra-red absorption spectrum of the compound shows a weak band at 3300 cm^{-1} indicating the participation of phenolic -OH group in complex formation. Absence of any band between 1350 cm^{-1} and 1500 cm^{-1} indicates tetravalent boron atom¹.

Syntheses and studies of similar boron chelates of anthranilhydroxamic acid, *o*-methoxy phenyl hydroxamic acid and different N-substituted salicyl and anthranil hydroxamic acids are in progress and will be communicated in due course.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Studies of Copper (II) with 2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenonethiosemicarbazone

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC studies on complex formation in Iron(III)-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone thiosemicarbazone (5MeOATS) system have been reported earlier¹. The present note describes similar studies with copper(II) and also some extraction studies.

Experimental

5-MeOATS was prepared as described earlier¹. The chloroform (B.D.H.) was used as an extracting solvent after purifying by the usual method.² Tech-

nical grade methanol used was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and then distilled. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving calculated amount of copper sulphate, and standardized by gravimetric and volumetric methods. Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Zeiss-Specol using matched 1 cm cells at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Vosburgh and Cooper³ method was employed to determine the nature of complexes in a 50% v/v methanol-water medium, keeping acidity constant at 0.2M HNO_3 . The results showed the presence of two complexes, one yellow and the other green. The former showed a continuously decreasing absorption over the entire visible region whereas the latter showed λ_{max} at 640 nm. To characterise the complexes the subsequent absorbance measurements were made at 430 nm and 640 nm, keeping the acidity constant at 0.2M HNO_3 and in 50% v/v methanol-water medium.

The composition of the complexes was determined by the Job's⁴ and Slope-ratio⁵ methods. The results showed that the stoichiometric ratio of copper(II)-5-MeOATS is 1 : 1 and 430 nm at 1 : 2 at 640 nm. It was further observed that the yellow coloured complex was found extracting into chloroform layer and therefore to characterise it further extraction studies were made as under.

Extraction Studies : General procedure :

Required volume of aqueous solution of copper(II) ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) and the alcoholic solution of reagent ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) were mixed in a 50 ml separatory funnel such that the resulting solution attain 50% v/v methanol-water medium. This was shaken for 15 min with 10 ml chloroform. After the layers were allowed to separate, the organic phase was withdrawn in a 25 ml conical flask. The absorbance of the yellow extract was measured at 430 nm against reagent blank.

The method of Vosburgh and Cooper² was employed to determine the nature of the complex species extracted into the chloroform layer. As there was no λ_{max} in the visible region, the subsequent absorbance measurements were made at 430 nm.

In order to determine the composition of the extracted complex, Job's⁴, Slope-ratio⁵, and Molar ratio⁶ methods were adopted for the extraction studies by Bhatki, Rane and Kabadi⁷. The absorbance measurements showed a stoichiometric ratio of copper to reagent of 1 : 1.

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Gravimetric Determination of Platinum with P-Dimethylaminoanil of 3-Phenanthryl Glyoxal

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IN our previous communication¹, chelates of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Pt(IV), Mn(II) and Fe(III) with *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-Phenanthryl glyoxal (ligand) have been prepared and characterised. It has been observed that ligand forms dark coloured chelates which are more or less soluble in acetone except Pt(IV) chelate. Ligand reacts quantitatively with Pt(IV) in acetone to give light grey precipitate. It is therefore thought worthwhile to carry gravimetric estimations of Pt(IV) with the ligand and to note the effect of various compounds present.

Preparation of the solutions: Reagent (*p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal²) was dissolved in acetone to prepare approximately 0.01M solution. Stock solution of H₂PtCl₆.6H₂O was prepared in acetone and standardised gravimetrically by the procedure described by Vogel³.

A known volume (2–65 ml) of platinum chloride was taken and diluted to 75–100 ml and the precipitant solution was added slowly with constant stirring; grey precipitate of platinum (IV) chelate is formed immediately. After allowing to stand for 15 min., the precipitate was filtered through sintered glass crucible, washed several times with dry acetone, dried in oven and weighed as Pt(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)Cl₄. Several experiments were performed by using different volumes of platinum chloride solution.

From the experimental results, it may be concluded that *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal can effectively be employed as a gravimetric

reagent for platinum. In the gravimetric experiments error found was of the order 1–2%. The precipitate is insoluble in 75% acetic acid acetone, ether, benzene and carbontetrachloride. *P*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal is tested as gravimetric reagent only for Pt(IV) in acetonic medium, hence this method may be regarded as of limited applicability. However, reagent is quite effective in 75% acetic acid medium also. Moreover, the reagent is quite specific in presence of nickel chloride, cupric chloride and bromide, cadmium chloride and acetate, ferric chloride, zinc chloride, manganese chloride and silver nitrate.

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Gravimetric Determination of Cadmium with the Ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline

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THE ligand has recently been used for the gravimetric determination of Cu(II) by the authors. In the present investigation the same ligand has further been used for the gravimetric determination of cadmium. Investigations have indicated that at pH 7.5 to 10 of the ligand, it reacts with Cd²⁺ ions giving precipitate of insoluble metal complex. The cadmium complex after settling is of orange red or brown red colour. The element analysis shows that the mole ratio of the metal to ligand is 1 : 2. The method is useful even if 0.5 mg of cadmium is present.

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade and the ligand was prepared by the method of Bagulev and Elvidge¹.

Element Analysis—Ligand	%C	%H	%N
Found	58.9	3.9	17.5
Required	59.3	3.7	17.3

The following stock solns. were prepared.

- (1) 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline...about 0.1% sodium salt soln. of the ligand in NaOH of pH 7.5 to 10.